

Determinants of Service Monopoly in Passenger Travelling: A Case on Starline Paribahan (Pvt.) Limited.

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Abstract

Higher expectations on services are very common to passenger for travelling whether for short or long-distance journey. It is aroused through independent, self service attitude of passengers to move without interruption with the righteous policy to be informed and connected. This study focused on the key factors having influence on selecting a transport for travelling. Due to varied nature of selection methods and variability, the factors were found disperse in different dimensions. In this study, the researcher craved to identify the impact of scattered factors that have been considered by the passengers to prefer Starline Paribahan (Pvt.) Limited and made some clusters through similarities and variability by Varimax Rotation Factor Analysis particularly for Feni region. From several factors, this study found that maximum preference toned with quality service, one stop service, price, brand belief, income and waiting time. It is expected that these factors will draw attention to policy makers, professionals and market participants for the enhancement of ensuring satisfaction in passenger travelling.

Keyword: One Stop Service, Travel Service, Passenger, Waiting Time.

Introduction

The transport sector in Bangladesh is termed as weak public and private institutions and low level of investment though it one of the most growing and profitable sectors in Bangladesh. However, the general quality of services at all levels and by all modes have been poor along with unreliable service operations and safety and security issues (Mahmud, Rahman, and Hasanat-E- Rabbi, 2012). Very specifically, the road sector of Bangladesh, one of the significant role players in transporting both passengers and freight, is the most likely investment option along with its inherent advantage to provide point to point service carrying over 80% to 88% as per the Bangladesh National Conservation Strategy, 2016. Again, quality of road score as per the infrastructure score report of Bangladesh was 2.9 particularly on roads according to the Global Competitiveness Report of the year 2014-15 of World Economic Forum.

Transport prices can be structured in various ways and price structures are affected through the consumer responses like timing, perceived cost structures, perceived fairness, attitudes, distances, age and gender (Bonsall, Dix, Stone, and Stewart, 2006); trip types, distances and users (Dargay, 2007); transport modes, and travel time (Small & Winston, 1999); population size & income (Burt & Hoover, 2006). For intercity bus carrier to get a competitive advantage, effective marketing strategies play the key role to endure in the long-distance transportation market whereas loyalty worked as a measure (Flavian, Martinez, and Polo, 2001). The attachment of loyalty is characterized by advocacy to others, resistance to change and relative preference of the brand in competition (Butcher, 2001), transport and travel cost and price purposes, fuel price (Buehler, 2010), household demographics, income and location (Whelan, 2007); vehicle types & traveling options (Giuliano and Dargay, 2006) and socioeconomic factors

and travel conditions (Karlaftis and Golias, 2002). Service companies particularly on transport, the brand/company needs to match resources to the demand by among the nature of demand, the capacity requirement and related risk measures on the basis of multiple influencing factors (Heskett, Sasser & Hart, 1990). By increasing facilities and capacity, it is possible to meet the increased demand in transportation system adopting "supply side" strategies (Wilson & Shirazi, 1991). Finally, to evaluate the travel and transport impacts, distance, real household income, age of head of household, number of children or family tour, employment status, occupational class, availability of transport, and density are considered as the most influential factors (Santos, McGuckin, Nakamoto, Gray, & Liss, 2011). That's why the study aims to develop and identify the transport related factors from the passengers' preference in this region.

Literature Review

Several studies have confirmed a direct positive relationship between satisfaction and loyalty (Andreassen and Lindestad, 1998; Bloemer and Kasper, 1995; Butcher, 2001; Cronin, Brady, and Hult, 2000; Dick and Basu, 1994; Fornell, Johnson, Anderson, & Bryant, 1996; Hellier, 2003; Stank, Goldsby, and Vickery, 1999; Ostrowski, O'Brien, and Gordon, 1993;) with the assumption that switching cost increases the intention of customer loyalty (Jones, Mothersbaugh, and Beatty, 2000; Lee and Cunningham, 2001). Desired service expectation is worked for being customers happy and worked as a heading factor against competitors (Davidow and Uttal, 1989). On the other hand, satisfaction is treated as an emotion based feeling or a degree of pleasure and contentment or a distance between performance and expectations in service (Bloemer and Kasper, 1995; Andreassen and Lindestad, 1998; Cronin et.al., 2000; Dick and Basu, 1994; Fornell et.al., 1996). Satisfied customers have a higher price tolerance for their preference and had less attraction for switching to competitors (Fornell et.al., 1996). True brand loyalty not only repeats purchasing behavior but also commits to brands through psychological and evaluative decision making approach (Bloemer and Kasper, 1995). Trust that lead to a higher level of loyalty (Morgan & Hunt, 1994) is based on the belief that guided to and motivated for favorable and positive intentions toward the welfare and interests of the object (Ballester and Aleman, 1999). Customer satisfaction is treated as one of the most frequently used indicators to measure the success of a marketing strategy (Flavian et. al., 2001). More specifically, customer loyalty is the degree to which the customer has exhibited repurchasing behavior of a particular company service and the significance of expenditure on that particular type of service (Hellier, 2003).

A deeply held commitment to re-buy or re-patronize a preferred product/service might cause repetitive same-brand or same brand set purchasing despite of situational influences. But marketing efforts had the potential to cause switching behavior (Oliver, 1997) and made the psychological attachment to a service (Beatty, Kahle, and Homer, 1988). Brand image focuses mental image of the consumer with symbolic meanings that associated with the specific attributes of a product or service (Cretu & Brodie, 2007; Dobni & Zinkhan, 1990). Price is a strong factor limiting the buying power or consumer choices and preference for price sensitive consumers. Discomfort, time of travel and risk are considerable factor for transport prices though changes in price affected through location decisions, vehicle type, type of service selected, frequency of (Litman, 2013). Service quality is addressed with expectation and

perceptions of service (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry, 1985) whereas the monetary price and the nonmonetary price particularly on time, search, and psychological costs would be considered under perceived price (Zeithaml, 1988; Dodds, Monroe, and Grewal, 1991). The earlier resulting statistics of May, Grant-Muller, Marsden, and Thanos (2008) tend to overlook or undercount off-peak travel, short trips, poor people's travel, children's travel, and non-motorized travel under the dimension of quality service in survey.

Finally, self - perceived service roles educate customers to understand their roles and how to perform better. In order to predict travel behavior, it is important to understand how individual characteristics of a person interact with the characteristics of the situation, therefore understanding the positive and negative evaluative factors influencing destination choices of the people are worth considerable (March & Woodside, 2005; Laws, 1995; Holloway, 2004). Waiting time works as an influential factor depending on urgency where in one stop service, no passenger should uplift other than counter.

Methodology

The study is descriptive in nature conducted by using a survey method. The population was the passengers travelling frequently from Feni to Chittagong, Bangladesh by using the Starline Paribahan Ltd. and other passenger transports. Structured questionnaire was used as a means of data collection and was collected via personally administered questionnaire. In total 220 passengers were randomly selected where response rate was 91% i.e., 200 respondents. The instrument was made up of sections of questions as per the factors in prearranged order. All items were measured on a five-point Likert Scale ranging from 1 'Strongly Disagree' to 5 'Strongly Agree'.

Analysis

Factors to be considered in selecting Starline Paribahan in Passenger Travelling Services:

Along with background data, the researcher is interested to know the characteristics of Starline transport service for satisfying the passengers and maintaining loyalty from both the passengers and few staffs/officials of Starline. The collected data then were analyzed by applying factor analysis using SPSS 22.0. The KMO value is 0.872 which indicates the sampling adequacy of data in table # 1. Again, based on the descriptive and communalities, table # 2 results that the mean for cleanliness (4.21) is the highest while seating capacity (2.07) is the lowest, though highest dispersion goes with area coverage (1.001).

Principal Component Analysis

The variables have been further subjected to principal component analysis. The Eigen values, the percentage of total variance, and rotated sum of squared loadings have been shown in Table-3 in appendix. The factor matrix as obtained in the principal component analysis has also been further subjected to Varimax Rotation. An examination of Eigen values has led to the retention of six factors according to table # 3. These factors have accumulated for

19.040%, 17.057%, 16.336%, 8.450%, 6.766%, & 6.076% of variation. This implies that the total variance accumulated for by all six factors is 73.725 % and remaining variance is explained by other factors.

Factor Analysis

The rotated factor matrix has been shown in Table- 4. This shows that variables understudy has constituted six groups/factors. It can be mentioned that the variable with factor loading of 0.423 and above has been considered for inclusion into the factors. These have been discussed in the following paragraphs.

Factor-I: Quality Service

Factor-I explains 19.040% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed this major cluster. This factor belongs to quality service, supervisor service, cleanliness, on time service, onboard conditions, and seating capacity. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension, which may be identified as '*Quality Service Factor*'.

Factor-II: One Stop Service

Factor-II explains 17.057% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed second important cluster. This factor is concerned with one stop service, no. of stoppage in between destination, accuracy of departure time, on time destination, passenger service policy and area coverage. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension, which may be identified as '*One Stop Service Factor*'.

Factor-III: Price

Factor-III explains 16.336% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed third cluster. This factor is concerned with reasonable fare, changes of fare in rush hour, price structure, easy purchase of ticket, daily tour, and competitor's price. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension which may be identified as '*Price Factor*'.

Factor-IV: Brand Belief

Factor-IV explains 8.450% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed fourth cluster. This factor belongs to brand belief, trust of passengers about service, availability of service, staff / personnel behavior, safety driving, no. of years in service, and prior experience. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension, which may be identified as '*Brand Belief Factor*'.

Factor-V: Income

Factor-V explains 6.766% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed fifth cluster. This factor is related to personal income, family income, family status, family background, passenger characteristics, and reason of tour. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension which may be identified as '*Income Factor*'.

Factor-VI: Waiting Time

Factor-VI explains 6.076% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed sixth cluster. This factor is related to certainty of service, service

frequency, continuation of service, service provision, no. of time of traveling and frequency of traveling. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension which may be identified as '*Waiting Time Factor*'.

Along with the Varimax Rotation analysis, goodness-of-fit test (table # 5) is also one of the tests used under maximum likelihood methods to test the data whether fit or not for scale differences and for an expected standardized population. The study covers this chi-square test only for checking the fitness of data, though this chi-square test's level of significance varies with sample sizes and size of correlations.

Discussion

The factors which draw attention to policy makers, professionals and market participants for the enhancement of ensuring satisfaction of Starline in passenger travelling services in particular and transport industry in general based on magnitudes like quality service, one stop service, price, brand belief, income and waiting time. However, this study reflected the context on satisfying the passengers in travelling in between Feni and Chittagong. The issue itself added a greater sense of urgency and purpose to deliberations, as well as hope that the considerable factors relating to passengers' preferences and desires might give ways to the other competitors i.e., passenger transport providers to offer in future and uphold a competitive service comparing to Starline.

On the other hand, Rystam (1998) suggested counting hard standard factors like travelling time, fare etc. and soft standard factors like comfort, information etc; the objective factors for transport services like gender, age, and trips related factors especially purpose and subjective factors like valuations of the alternative's characteristics, attitudes and lifestyle. These factors are based on the individual's perceptions and are often more difficult to quantify. Finally, the transport related attributes that better describe the travel standard are timetable, comfort and service factors, and quality satisfaction and safety (Kottenhoff, 1999). The practices and consideration of those factor might mitigate the abundance opts of a particular service provider in this region. So, these findings are also similar to the earlier studies of Andreassen and Lindestad (1998) and Hellier (2003) that identify the direct positive relationship considering the important factors of satisfaction and loyalty. Ultimately these factors also worked for creating desired service expectation in the long run and also worked for being customers happy and preferential competitors according to the findings of Davidow and Uttal (1989). In this study, price is one of the crucial factors because of the assumption that satisfied customers have a higher price tolerance for their preference and had less attraction for switching to competitors (Fornell et.al., 1996).

In a nutshell, these findings are consistent with prior studies that suggest service quality and affordability are major determinants of passenger satisfaction and loyalty. The clustering of factors further underscores the interdependence between tangible elements such as pricing and waiting time, and intangible elements such as brand trust and perceived service reliability. Moreover, these outcomes reflect that passengers not only seek cost-effective options but also value convenience, punctuality, and the overall experience of the journey. From a practical standpoint, the results have significant implications for transport service providers and policymakers. Service providers must

maintain and improve quality standards while balancing competitive pricing strategies. Reducing waiting times through better scheduling and enhancing brand credibility through consistent service delivery could further strengthen passenger loyalty. Policymakers may use these insights to design regulations and infrastructure that support more seamless travel experiences in the Feni region and beyond.

Conclusion

This study concludes that passengers' selection of Starline Paribahan (Pvt.) Limited is significantly influenced by a combination of service quality, convenience, price, brand trust, income, and waiting time. These key factors collectively shape passenger preferences and their overall satisfaction with travel services. These findings suggest that continuous improvement in these areas will not only attract more passengers but also contribute to long-term customer retention and brand strength. Future research may explore additional psychological and behavioral aspects that affect travel decisions, as well as compare these findings with other transport service providers to gain a broader understanding of regional and national trends. In fine, the replication of this study is also possible through expanding the scope of coverage in future for better accuracy of identifying influential factors of transport sector of Bangladesh. By addressing these critical factors, transport operators and policymakers can foster a more efficient, customer-centered transportation system that meets the rising expectations of passengers.

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Table # 1: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.872
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	14708.160
	df	741
	Sig.	.000

Table #2: Descriptive Statistics & Communalities

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Extraction
Quality service	4.09	.613	.730
Supervisor service	4.16	.650	.733
Cleanliness	4.21	.642	.751
On-time service	2.34	.916	.753
Onboard conditions	2.29	.942	.728
Seating capacity	2.07	.815	.745

One stop service	2.17	.902	.747
No. of stoppage in between destination	2.24	.853	.718
Accuracy of departure time	2.64	.958	.615
On time destination	3.21	.945	.621
Passenger service policy	2.45	.934	.493
Area coverage	2.69	1.001	.602
Price	3.79	.803	.570
Reasonable fare	3.84	.778	.694
changes of fare in rush hour	3.87	.762	.731
Price structure	3.74	.764	.704
Easy purchase of ticket	3.74	.733	.737
Daily tour	3.81	.772	.621
Competitor's price	3.25	.882	.364
Brand belief	3.44	.863	.611
Trust of passengers about service	3.49	.937	.777
Availability of service	3.49	.881	.746
Staff / personnel behavior	3.67	.844	.806
Safety driving	3.31	.977	.661
No. Of years in service	3.71	.846	.781
Prior experience	2.66	.763	.509
Personal income	2.81	.850	.786
Family income	2.68	.854	.618
Family status	3.15	.901	.628
Family background	2.98	.896	.723
Passenger characteristics	3.00	.908	.806
Reason of tour	2.86	.845	.600
Waiting time	4.00	.721	.698
Certainty of service	3.96	.702	.791
Service frequency	3.98	.724	.811
Continuation of service	3.98	.699	.829
Service provision	4.04	.736	.781
No. of times of traveling	4.04	.723	.726
Frequency of traveling	4.02	.701	.647

Table-3: Total Variance Explained

Component	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings
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	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	19.586	36.955	36.955	10.091	19.04	19.04
2	7.459	14.073	51.028	9.04	17.057	36.097
3	4.928	9.298	60.326	8.658	16.336	52.433
4	4.055	7.651	67.977	4.478	8.45	60.883
5	3.53	6.661	74.638	3.586	6.766	67.649
6	2.373	4.477	79.115	3.22	6.076	73.725

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table-4: Rotated Component Matrix

Component	1	2	3	4	5	6
Quality service	0.946	0.012	0.033	0.075	-0.1	0.096
Supervisor service	0.872	0.276	0.291	0.059	0.129	0
Cleanliness	0.743	0.481	0.339	0.084	0.013	-0.127
On-time service	0.705	-0.208	0.473	0.19	0.311	0.219
Onboard conditions	0.689	-0.348	0.255	0.053	0.041	0.145
Seating capacity	0.677	0.203	0.261	0.4	0.212	0.202
One stop service	0.395	0.669	-0.258	0.077	0.362	0.276
No. of stoppage in between destination	0.339	0.66	0.444	0.069	0.11	-0.122
Accuracy of departure time	0.473	0.645	-0.223	-0.008	-0.37	-0.239
On time destination	0.07	0.824	0.422	-0.036	0.116	-0.005
Passenger service policy	0.255	0.853	0.025	-0.293	-0.086	0.169
Area coverage	0.034	0.832	0.329	0.218	0.101	-0.149
Price	0.257	0.395	0.778	0.074	-0.176	0.237
Reasonable fare	0.121	0.339	0.761	0.027	-0.029	0.008
Changes of fare in rush hour	0.01	0.473	0.745	0.138	-0.179	-0.236
Price structure	0.115	0.255	0.833	0.146	0.332	-0.009
Easy purchase of ticket	0.274	0.195	0.832	-0.102	0.226	-0.074
Daily tour	0.031	-0.021	0.825	-0.048	-0.121	-0.163
Competitor's price	0.335	0.075	0.773	0.263	-0.201	-0.284
Brand belief	0.031	-0.112	0.065	0.873	0.101	0.226
Trust of passengers about service	-0.099	0.337	-0.156	0.743	0.129	0.041
Availability of service	0.224	-0.155	0.246	0.714	0.157	0.135
Staff / personnel behavior	0.196	0.496	0.119	0.5	0.478	-0.118
Safety driving	0.441	0.164	-0.442	0.423	0.26	0.106
No. of years in service	0.221	0.356	0.161	0.739	-0.016	0.236

Prior experience	0.353	0.473	0.014	0.627	0.001	-0.222
Personal income	0.282	0.308	0.499	-0.093	0.546	-0.236
Family income	0.344	0.084	0.41	0.533	0.535	-0.04
Family status	0.22	0.296	0.069	0.222	0.7	0.046
Family background	0.637	0.043	0.172	-0.129	0.67	0.035
Passenger characteristics	-0.132	-0.255	-0.099	-0.115	0.629	-0.145
Reason of tour	0.069	0.007	-0.016	0.054	0.959	-0.118
Waiting time	0.171	-0.207	0.134	0.389	-0.01	0.607
Certainty of service	0.014	0.164	0.187	0.027	0.178	0.759
Service frequency	0.183	-0.228	-0.036	-0.08	-0.002	0.73
Continuation of service	0.11	0.025	-0.126	-0.06	0.184	0.713
Service provision	-0.044	0.052	0.243	0.109	0.083	0.671
No. of times of traveling	0.086	0.066	0.166	-0.004	-0.141	0.581
Frequency of traveling	0.209	-0.218	-0.02	0.15	-0.266	0.662

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a Rotation converged in 21 iterations.

Table # 5: Goodness-of-fit Test

Chi-Square	df	Sig.
2808.302	522	.000